

LANDSCAPE CHARACTER TYPE SELECTION	CLIMATE	PARENT MATERIAL	PHYSIOGRAPHIC CLUSTERS	AREA (SQ.KM)
	ALTITUDE	LANDCOVER		

LANDSCAPE DESCRIPTION

S/N	Landscape Type	Climate Class	Geology Class	Elevation Class	Landcover Class	Landscape Shape Index	Total Area (Sq.Km)	Prop. of Landscape	No. of Patches	Largest Patch Index	Edge Density	Total Edges (Millions)
1	C1G4E1L10	Tropical wet	Sedimentary rock formation	Very Low (0-100m)	Tree Cover	6.40	6,380	0.68	22	0.166	0.0162	1,517,844
2	C1G4E1L30	Tropical wet	Sedimentary rock formation	Very Low (0-100m)	Grassland	4.13	333	0.03	10	0.014	0.0025	238,888
3	C1G4E1L50	Tropical wet	Sedimentary rock formation	Very Low (0-100m)	Built-up	2.68	228	0.03	5	0.014	0.0012	115,610
4	C1G4E1L60	Tropical wet	Sedimentary rock formation	Very Low (0-100m)	Bare land	1.39	15	0.00	1	0.002	0.0002	14,765
5	C1G4E1L80	Tropical wet	Sedimentary rock formation	Very Low (0-100m)	Waterbody	2.84	103	0.01	7	0.005	0.0012	110,692
6	C1G4E1L90	Tropical wet	Sedimentary rock formation	Very Low (0-100m)	Wetland	2.63	47	0.00	2	0.002	0.0005	46,714
7	C1G4E1L95	Tropical wet	Sedimentary rock formation	Very Low (0-100m)	Mangroves	4.16	9,301	0.99	5	0.640	0.0114	1,070,533
8	C2G4E1L10	Tropical wet and dry	Sedimentary rock formation	Very Low (0-100m)	Tree Cover	8.73	57,751	6.15	33	5.908	0.0869	8,161,449
9	C2G4E1L20	Tropical wet and dry	Sedimentary rock formation	Very Low (0-100m)	Shrubland	3.16	130	0.01	6	0.005	0.0016	146,646
10	C2G4E1L30	Tropical wet and dry	Sedimentary rock formation	Very Low (0-100m)	Grassland	11.34	4,228	0.45	72	0.070	0.0315	2,963,330
11	C2G4E1L40	Tropical wet and dry	Sedimentary rock formation	Very Low (0-100m)	Cropland	5.68	1,022	0.11	10	0.022	0.0070	728,069